

A Case Report on Thymoma Related Pure White Cell Aplasia

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ABSTRACT

We depicted an interesting case of a Chinese woman with history of metastatic thymoma presented with fever and severe neutropenia subsequently found to have agranulocytosis in bone marrow exam. A rare diagnosis of thymoma related pure white cell aplasia has to be considered.

Keywords: Thymus Neoplasms; Agranulocytosis

CASE REPORT

A 65-year-old Chinese woman first presented in June 2013 to a local hospital for retrosternal discomfort and weight loss. She had no paraneoplastic manifestation and her blood tests were unremarkable. CT thorax showed a 9cm anterior mediastinal mass with multiple pleural based nodules up to 3cm in size. (Figure 1A) A CT guided biopsy was obtained, histology showed WHO type B1 (lymphocyte predominant) thymoma.

In view of the presence of multiple pleural metastases, operation was not recommended. She was started on palliative chemotherapy Etoposide- Cisplatin for six cycles followed by palliative radiotherapy to the mediastinum 30Gy in 10 fractions over 2 weeks. Treatment was completed by April 2014 with progress CT scan showing partial response. (Figure 1B) Subsequent follow-up CT scans only showed mild interval enlargement of the pleural nodules. In view of slow progression and asymptomatic, she was therefore put on drug holiday from 2014 to 2020. She underwent left mastectomy for an early screen-detected (4.5mm) Stage I breast cancer in March 2018, for which no adjuvant treatment was given.

She complained of progressive weight loss and left neck swelling in July 2020. PET/CT showed multiple hypermetabolic lymphadenopathy including supraclavicular, axillary, inguinal and intra-abdominal lymph nodes. Marked progression of the mediastinal and residual pleural lesions were also evident. (Figure 1C) Fine needle aspiration of the left supraclavicular node yielded necrotic tissue later confirmed to be positive for Mycobacterium Tuberculosis. She was started on anti-tuberculosis treatment with Isoniazid, Ethambutol, Pyrazinamide and Rifampicin since August 2020. By that time, her blood counts were unremarkable. Palliative systemic treatment for thymoma was not initiated in view of active infection.

On 20th October 2020, she was admitted via the A&E department for two days history of high fever up to 39.2°C, sore throat and dysphagia. On admission, her total white cell count was 0.67×10^9 with absolute neutrophil count

(ANC) of 0.03×10^9 . She was put on broad spectrum antimicrobials as well as G-CSF support. Anti-TB medications were also stopped due to concern about drug induced neutropenia. Autoimmune screening only showed a weakly positive anti-nuclear antibody titre. The serum immunoglobulins were within the normal range. There was no clinical improvement after a week of treatment. The patient had persistent dysphagia and neutropenia with ANC consistently below 0.04×10^9 . An upper endoscopy showed features suggestive of candidiasis of the oesophagus with whitish slough like mural thickening near the gastro-oesophageal junction. Micafungin was started since 4th November 2020. The biopsy later confirmed to be positive for MTB-PCR.

A bone marrow examination was performed eventually on 5th November 2020. There was virtual absence of granulocyte in the peripheral blood smear (Figure 2A) and absence of granulocytic precursors in the marrow and trephine sections (Figure 2B/2C). Erythropoiesis and megakaryocytes were adequate. Immunohistochemical staining did not show infiltration by epithelial malignancy, Ziehl-Neelsen and GMS stains did not show evidence of acid-fast bacilli or fungal infiltration. T cell receptor gene rearrangement study was negative for clonal expansion of CD8+ T cells. She was reviewed by haematologist, the diagnosis of pure white cell aplasia associated with pure white cell aplasia was established by exclusion.

The patient was given a trial of intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIg) and her anti-tuberculosis treatment was resumed on 10th November 2020. There was however no improvement in blood count. She was started on oral cyclophosphamide since 17th November 2020 for its immunomodulatory effect. Again, the clinical response was not apparent. The patient eventually developed severe hospital acquired pneumonia due to the prolonged neutropenia and succumbed on 27th November 2020.

Figure 1A: Initial CT at diagnosis in August 2013 showing anterior mediastinal mass (Red arrow) and pleural based nodule (Yellow arrow)

Figure 1B: Progress CT in June 2014 after treatment with chemotherapy and radiotherapy. The anterior mediastinal mass showed significant shrinkage (yellow arrow) though there was mild interval increase in pleural nodules (red arrow)

Figure 1C: Gross disease progression with marked enlargement of the mediastinal and pleural mass

Figure 2A: Peripheral blood smear (400x) showing absence of granulocytes

Figure 2B: Bone marrow aspirate (400x) demonstrated normal erythrocyte and megakaryocyte progenitors but absence of granulocytic precursors.

Figure 2C: Trephine section (400x) showed mildly hypocellular marrow with absent granulopoiesis

DISCUSSION

Thymus neoplasms are uncommon and they usually present at an advanced stage due to atypical symptoms. As thymus is an important organ for maturation of T lymphocytes, patients with thymoma can present with a range of immune-mediated paraneoplastic manifestation. The five most common presentations include myasthenia gravis, red cell aplasia, lichen planus, Good's syndrome and limbic encephalitis.^[1]

Pure white cell aplasia (PWCA) is a recognized but rare paraneoplastic manifestation of thymus neoplasms. There has been several reports on thymoma related PWCA in the past two decades (refer to Table 1). The most common presentation is persistent fever, although other immune related phenomenon such as endocrinopathies (thyroiditis and type I diabetes) has been reported ^[2], suggesting that its pathogenesis could be related to autoantibody. Bone marrow morphology is characterized by the absence of myelopoietic activities but preservation of erythropoiesis and megakaryopoiesis. Occasionally, the presence of monoclonal T-cell receptor gene rearrangement can be detected, similar to those of pure red cell aplasia.

Invariably all of the report cases in remission underwent surgical resection of the thymus. This is consistent with the study on myasthenia gravis in which thymectomy was shown to improve clinic outcomes for localized disease, suggesting the presence of thymus plays a central role in these paraneoplastic conditions. However, the role of thymectomy in metastatic disease is uncertain in controlling paraneoplastic symptoms. In contrary to other paraneoplastic syndromes in solid cancers attributed to endogenous production of excessive cytokines and hormones (e.g. PTH, ACTH, VEGF etc.), there seems to be no established relationship between disease burden or stage at presentation with the occurrence of paraneoplastic manifestations in thymoma.

Cyclosporin A has been widely used^[2-5]; it produces a modest effect on neutrophil count and serves as a good maintenance therapy in some cases. IVIg was not shown to be effective. G-CSF alone rarely leads to significant improvement and must be coupled with other treatment modalities. Interestingly, Campath-1H (Monoclonal anti-CD52 antibody) has successfully induced remission in one case of PWCA refractory to immunosuppressant and plasmapheresis.^[5]

Table 1: Summary of cases of PWCA associated with thymus neoplasm

Sex/Age	Histology	Presentation	Treatment	Outcome
F/76 ^[2]	Type B2 thymoma	Type I diabetes Thyroiditis Fever	Pulsed steroid IVIg G-CSF Cyclosporin A Thymectomy	Responded with maintenance steroid and CsA
F/65 ^[3]	Mixed Type A and B2 thymoma	Fever and rash Night sweats	IVIg G-CSF Cyclosporin A Thymectomy	Responded and weaned off CsA after 6 months
M/63 ^[4]	Type A thymoma	Persistent fever	G-CSF Cyclosporin A Thymectomy	ANC normalized few days after CsA Long term remission after thymectomy
M/59 ^[5]	Type A thymoma	Fever and oral ulcers	G-CSF Thymectomy Plasmapheresis Cyclosporin A MMF Campath-1H	Campath-1H induced remission of refractory neutropenia

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

All authors have disclosed no conflicts of interest.

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ETHICS APPROVAL

The patient was treated in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. The patient provided written informed consent for all treatments and procedures.

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